

Synthesis of novel 3-substituted derivatives of 2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-one moiety

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Abstract : New 3-substituted-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile were prepared by cyclisation of 5-methyl-6-cyano-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-3-carbohydrazide and 3-(5-methyl thiosemicarbazide)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile with different cyclization reagents. The structures of all compounds synthesized were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, IR and ¹H NMR spectral data.

Keywords : 2*H*-Pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-one, antibacterial activity, cyclisation.

Pyranopyridines are an important compounds in the synthesis of biological active¹ and chemically interesting molecules due to their structural similarity to coumarines². The biological activity of the compounds containing this basic moiety has been well documented³. Some of them like amlexanox (anti-allergic, anti-asthmatic), pranoprofen (anti-inflammatory) and traxanox (anti-allergic, anti-asthmatic) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

The synthesis of compounds incorporating 1,2,4-triazoles and 1,3,4-thiadiazole rings has been attracting widespread attention due to their pharmacological properties such as antimicrobial⁴, hypoglycemic⁵, diuretic⁶, antiviral⁷ and anti-inflammatory⁸. In addition, several 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives have been reported to possess diverse biological activities. In view of above findings, it was thought that it would be worthwhile to design and synthesize compounds containing some 1,3,4-oxadiazoles, 1,3,4-thiadiazoles and 1,2,4-triazoles having a 2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-one moiety and screen them for potential biological activities. We have previously reported the synthesis of some novel and

biologically active 2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-one and analogs in connection with our on-going project on bioactive 2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-one and analogs⁹. In continuation of our interest to work on bioactive 2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-one, we now wish to report our results towards the synthesis of some novel 3-substituted-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile.

Results and discussion

5-Methyl-6-cyano-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-3-carbohydrazide **2**, was conveniently prepared from ethyl-5-methyl-6-cyano-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-3-carboxylate **1**^{9a} with hydrazine hydrate under ethanol reflux, followed by normal workup affording **2** with 90% yield. In the IR spectra of the compound **2** disappearance of the characteristic peak of ester at 1750 cm⁻¹ was observed, new signals belonging to the -NH₂ group was observed at 3348 cm⁻¹, in ¹H NMR spectra while the signals originating from the ester group triplet at δ 1.20–1.27 (*J* 7.07 Hz) for -CH₂CH₃, singlet for -CH₃ at δ 2.43 were disappeared.

3-(5-Sulfanyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile **3a** was obtained by the reaction of carbon disulphide with **2** in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide¹⁰. The carbohydrazide **2** was transformed to 3-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile **3b** in the presence of cyanogen bromide in ethanol¹¹. **2** was further cyclized to react with acid chlorides like acetyl chloride and benzoyl chloride to afford

Scheme 1

3-(5-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]pyridine-6-carbonytrile **3c** and 3-(5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]pyridine-6-carbonytrile **3d** respectively (Scheme 1).

Further the compound was reacted with methyl isothiocyanate in ethanol to obtain 3-(5-methyl thiosemicarbazide)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]pyridine-6-carbonytrile **4**. Compound **4** was cyclized through dehydration under heating with 2*N* sodium hydroxide solution to afford 3-(4-methyl-sulfanyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]pyridine-6-carbonytrile **5a**. 3-(5-Methyl amino-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]pyridine-6-carbonytrile **5b** was obtained by cyclisation of **4** by using iodine and potassium iodide in ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution. **4** was cyclized to get 3-(5-methyl amino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]pyridine-6-carbonytrile **5c** under heating with conc. H₂SO₄ (Scheme 2). All the compounds synthesized were characterized on the basis of analytical and spectral data.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on Buchi 545 melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 1650 spectrometer, ¹H NMR was recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ using 200 MHz Bruker spectrometer

Scheme 2

(chemical shifts in δ ppm) with TMS as internal standard. All the organic extracts were dried over sodium sulfate after work-up. The reactions were carried out under nitrogen with magnetic/mechanical stirring. Unless otherwise mentioned all the solvents and reagents used were of LR grade. TLC was performed on precoated silica-gel plates, which were visualized using UV light.

Synthesis of 5-methyl-6-cyano-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano-[2,3-b]pyridine-3-carbohydrazide (2): A mixture of compound ethyl-5-methyl-6-cyano-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]pyridine-3-carboxylate **1** (15 g, 0.054 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (20.8 g, 0.416 mol) in presence of ethanol (75 mL) was refluxed for 12–15 h, the progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC, after completion of the reaction, the excess ethanol was distilled off and the solid mass that separated out on cooling was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to obtain the compound **2** as a yellow solid, yield 90%; m.p. 350–352 °C (Found : C, 50.77; H, 3.16; N, 21.51. Calcd. for C₁₁H₈N₄O₄ : C, 50.82; H, 3.16; N, 21.59%); IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 3424 (-OH), 3348 (-NH₂), 2216 (-CN), 1706 (-C=O, lactone), 1650, (-C=O), amide); ¹H NMR 200 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 2.30 (s, -CH₃), 6.80 (1H, b, NH₂, D₂O exchangeable), 7.89 (1H, s, C₄-H).

Synthesis of 3-(5-sulfanyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]pyridine-6-carbonytrile (3a): A mixture of 5-methyl-6-cyano-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]pyridine-3-carbohydrazide **2** (10 g, 0.038 mol), potassium hydroxide (0.212 g, 0.0038 mol) and carbon disulphide (5 mL) in ethanol (50 mL) was refluxed on a steam bath for 8–10 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC. The solution of the reaction mass was cooled and concentrated. The resulting solution was acidified with dil. HCl and allowed to stand for 12 h. The separated solid was dried and crystallized from ethanol to obtain **3a**, yield 81%, m.p. 352–355 °C (Found : C, 47.63; H, 2.06; N, 18.63; S, 10.52. Calcd. for C₁₂H₆N₄O₄S : C, 47.73; H, 2.07; N, 18.59; S, 10.66%); IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 3070 (-OH), 2204 (-CN), 1720 (-C=O, lactone), 1637 (-C=O, amide); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 2.17 (1H, s, -SH), 2.27 (3H, s, -CH₃), 7.86 (1H, s, C₄-H).

Synthesis of 3-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]pyridine-6-carbonytrile (3b): A mixture of 5-methyl-6-cyano-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]pyridine-3-carbohydrazide **2** (12 g, 0.046 mol) and ethanol (50 mL), cyanogen bromide (4.89 g, 0.046 mol) was added, the mixture was warmed at 55–60 °C for 30 min. The reaction was monitored by TLC. The resulting clear solution was cooled and neutralized with sodium bicarbonate solution and allowed stand for 4 h. The solid thus separated

was filtered to obtain **3b** in the pure form, yield 84%, m.p. 394–396 °C (Found : C, 50.62; H, 2.50; N, 24.52. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_7N_5O_4$: C, 50.50; H, 2.51; N, 24.59%; IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3378, (-NH₂), 3104 (-OH), 2216 (-CN), 1710 (-C=O, lactone); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 2.53 (3H, s, -CH₃), 7.89 (1H, s, C₄-H).

General procedure for the preparation of 3c-d : A mixture of 5-methyl-6-cyano-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-3-carbohydrazide (**2**) (10 g, 0.038 mol) and acetyl chloride refluxed for 6-8 h, reaction was monitored by TLC after completion of the reaction. The excess acetic acid was distilled off and water was added to it, stirred for 2–3 h to precipitate the solid and filter to yield **3c-d**.

3-(5-Methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile 3c : Yield 89%, m.p. 400 °C (Found : C, 54.82; H, 2.91; N, 19.71. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_8N_4O_4$: C, 54.99; H, 2.90; N, 19.78%; IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3324 (-OH), 2218 (-CN), 1702 (-C=O, lactone); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 1.90 (3H, s, -CH₃), 2.35 (3H, s, -CH₃), 8.16 (1H, s, C₄-H).

3-(5-Phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile 3d : Yield 78%, m.p. 410 °C (Found : C, 62.31; H, 2.99; N, 16.20. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{10}N_4O_4$: C, 62.47; H, 2.98; N, 16.26%; IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3271 (-OH), 2214 (-CN), 1715 (-C=O, lactone); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 2.35 (3H, s, -CH₃), 7.18–7.31 (3H, m, Ar), 7.50 (1H, s, C₄-H), 8.20 (2H, m, Ar).

Synthesis of 3-(5-methyl thiosemicarbazide)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile (4) : The compound 5-methyl-6-cyano-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-3-carbohydrazide **2** (12 g, 0.046 mol) and methyl isothiocyanate (3.45 g, 0.046 mol) in ethanol (50 mL) refluxed for 3–4 h, the progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction mass was concentrated and cooled to obtain solid, this was collected by filtration. The separated solid was dried and crystallized from ethanol to obtain **4**, yield 72%; m.p. 345–347 °C (Found : C, 46.80; H, 3.41; N, 21.13; S, 9.66. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{11}N_5O_4S$: C, 46.91; H, 3.40; N, 21.07; S, 9.69%; IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3433 (-OH), 3215 (-NH), 2213 (-CN), 1708 (-C=O, lactone), 1624 (-C=O, amide); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 2.40 (s, -CH₃), 2.83 (3H, d, -CH₃), 7.9 (1H, b, -NH₂, exchangeable), 8.40 (1H, s, C₄-H).

Synthesis of 3-(4-methyl-sulfanyl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile (5a) : A mixture of 3-(5-methyl thiosemicarbazide)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile **6** (10 g, 0.03 mol) was

reacted with 2 *N* NaOH at reflux condition for 4 h. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction mass was poured into crushed ice and acidified with acetic acid. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from ethanol to get **5a**, yield 65%; m.p. 322–324 °C (Found : C, 49.74; H, 2.90; N, 22.19; S, 10.17. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_9N_5O_3S$: C, 49.57; H, 2.92; N, 22.26; S, 10.23%; IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3245 (-OH), 2226 (-CN), 1716 (-C=O, lactone), 1623 (-C=O, amide); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 1.80 (1H, s, -SH), 2.19 (3H, s, -CH₃), 2.35 (3H, s, -CH₃), 8.16 (1H, s, C₄-H).

Synthesis of 3-(5-methyl amino-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile (5b) : A mixture of 3-(5-methyl thiosemicarbazide)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile **6** (10 g, 0.03 mol) was suspended in ethanol was dissolved in cold aq. NaOH (4 *N*, 1 mL) at 0 °C. To this clear solution, iodine in aq. KI (5%) was added gradually with stirring till the color of iodine persisted at room temperature. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 2 h, cooled and poured into ice water. The precipitated solid was filtered to obtain **5b**, yield 60%, m.p. 380–382 °C (Found : C, 52.16; H, 3.12; N, 23.40. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_9N_5O_4$: C, 52.25; H, 3.11; N, 23.48%; IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3408 (-OH), 2204 (-CN), 1718 (-C=O, lactone); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 1.90 (s, -CH₃), 2.35 (3H, s, -CH₃), (1H, s, C₄-H).

Synthesis of 3-(5-methyl amino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile (5c) : A mixture of 3-(5-methyl thiosemicarbazide)-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano[2,3-*b*]pyridine-6-carbonytrile **6** (10 g, 0.03 mol) was dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid (50 mL) and stirred at room temperature for 24 h and then poured into crushed ice. The compound was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from ethanol to obtain **5c**, yield 54%, m.p. 296–298 °C (Found : C, 49.70; H, 2.93; N, 22.20; S, 10.20. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_9N_5O_3S$: C, 49.57; H, 2.92; N, 22.26; S, 10.23%; IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3314 (-CH), 2214 (-CN), 1732 (-C=O, lactone); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 2.51 (s, -CH₃), 2.99 (s, -CH₃), 7.45 (1H, s, C₄-H).

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Note

References

- (a) L. W. Robert and W. F. Paul, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **71**, 596; (b) S. Reinhard, W. G. Steven, M. W. Willard, C. S. Archie, W. S. Todd and A. B. Thomas, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1990, **33**, 1859; (c) Y. R. Bahia, O. A. Abdou, A. K. Fathy and E. S. Youssry, *Arch. Pharma. Res.*, 1989, **12**, 201.
- (a) K. Tsuneo, S. Susumu and M. Masayuki, Eur. Pat. Appl. EP 259811 A2 1988; (b) O. Z. Irina, M. K. Sergiy, V. I. Alexandre, P. C. Valentin and E. S. Pavlo, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2004, **41**, 517.
- (a) A. K. Nohara, H. Sugihara and K. Ukawa, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1985, **28**, 559; (b) M. Nakanishi, O. Takanori and M. F. Tsuruda, U.S. Pat. 3,931,205/1976 (*Chem. Abstr.* 1976, **84**, 135515); (c) T. N. Oe and M. Tsuruda, U.S. Pat. 4,085,111/1978.
- (a) M. B. Talwar, S. R. Desai, Y. S. Somannavar, S. C. Marihal and S. C. Bennur, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1996, **5**, 215; (b) M. B. Talwar, U. V. Laddi, R. S. Bennur and S. C. Bennur, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1994, **4**, 111; (c) T. Ikeda and K. Tada, Eur. Pat. 262,589/1988 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **109**, 7354).
- M. Y. Mhasalkar, M. H. Shah, S. T. Nikam, K. G. Anantnarayanan and C. V. Deliwala, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 672.
- G. Buquet, C. Fauran, C. Douzon, G. Raynad and J. Thomas, Fr. Demande, 2,215,949/1974 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, **82**, 156324).
- N. Srivastava, S. Bahadur, H. N. Verma and M. M. Khan, *Curr. Sci.*, 1984, **53**, 235.
- (a) M. Amir and R. Agarwal, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1998, **7**, 225; (b) M. C. Hosur, M. B. Talwar, S. C. Bennur, P. A. Patel and S. Sembrekar, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1993, **55**, 86; (c) M. D. Mullican, M. W. Wilson, D. T. Conner, C. R. Kostlan, D. J. Schrier and R. D. Dyer, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1993, **36**, 1090; (d) P. C. Unangst, G. P. Shrum, D. T. Conner, R. D. Dyer and D. J. Schrier, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1992, **35**, 3691.
- (a) N. Vasanth Kumar and Uday C. Mashelkar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2006, **45**, 1770; (b) 2007, **46**, 216.
- M. E. Abd Ei-Fattah, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1998, **8**, 111.
- M. Amir and S. Shahani, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1998, **8**, 107.